

3rd International Queer Buddhist Conference – IQBC, October 27–29, 2023

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Preface

After the 1st International Queer Buddhist Conference, IQBC, in 2021, which I founded to share a safe space for me and my siblings, queers, especially queer Buddhists, and mindful or respectful people, whether they are atheists, or of different religions, and also supportive allies, we meanwhile had the 3rd IQBC, and IQBC has become a yearly gathering.

This year we were blessed, because the famous black queer Buddhist teacher, Lama Rod Owens had agreed to be the keynote speaker of the 3rd IQBC. This was a great pleasure! He spoke freely and also mentioned his new book, „The New Saints“, which was published on Halloween, two days after the conference.

I was lucky that I was supported again by people, volunteers, who helped me organizing this conference, like my beautiful webmaster, Melanie, a supportive ally, and yoga teacher, and her partner, Lukas, giving advice when technical difficulties occur. Also I would like to mention Miriam, my longterm friend from the times we studied at the university. She is also an ally, a Jew, and she created the phenomenal virtual space in gather.town, where you could watch the exhibitions from e.g. Noire LaZard, or films from Ceikaiyia Cheeks and others, books like from Icaro Matias, or go on stage for the open mic, if you were courageous enough! ;)

But you also could meet there with old or new friends during the conference for private chats or be there in this beautiful surrounding and meditate, maybe at the fountain, or the river listening to the water and the birds, and many more beautiful spaces, like the Zen garden or the library, talking about queer or Buddhist books etc.

We had so many beautiful contributors, some I already mentioned. But I would like to mention some more, like Professor Stephen Kerry from Charles Darwin University, Australia, with their talk, or Stephanie Kolton from Patchwork Transgender Peer Support with workshop and seminar. Noire LaZard, I would like to mention with her amazing arts and a workshop with open conversation, or Jemarc Axinto, Trauma Recovery Coach, my Happy Buddha, s. the Happy Buddha rap on the IQBC Youtube Channel or on <https://www.drwurst.de/publikationen-raps/>, and more on this three days conference!

It was a big challenge to organize this conference virtually coming together from the West Coast of the US to the East Coast, Asia, Australia, and Europe. And in addition having a time change in Europe from summertime to wintertime during the conference. These conference proceedings only build an excerpt about the variation or diversity on this 3rd IQBC. We did not record the workshops due to the safety of the attendees, but we were allowed to record the Inclusivity workshop of Sibling Yonten, without Q&A. They is also one of the volunteers of the organizing team. Sibling Yonten from Plum Village UK is a beautiful supporter or volunteer of the IQBC since the 2nd IQBC, and they not only shared a workshop but also a warmhearted meditation, which attracted also people, who do not identify as queer or Buddhist.

But luckily the consent was given for the talks to be recorded as videos, which you can watch on <https://iqbc.org/recordings-iqbc-2023/> or on YouTube, where you can give a like, if you want to. Thank you!

Kyle Neo, free lance designer and writer had prepared an interactive „Buddhist toolkit“, a two days workshop with a beautiful team of three additional volunteers from Rainbodhi Singapore.

And Antony Arrien held his Workshop, in spite of a power outage, driving with his car and his smartphone searching for a Wi-Fi hotspot and holding his workshop finally from a parking place in his car. Awesome!

As I mentioned, we had beautiful scholars and respected venerables from different countries, not to forget Kody Muncaster, who is working on their dissertational thesis, but couldn't attend on the conference. They was so kind to send their amazing talk as video, which you luckily also can watch as mentioned before.

It seems again that after the conference, means before the conference, because people already asked for the 4th IQBC, and we are already thinking about the 4th International Queer Buddhist Conference, IQBC in 2024. Meanwhile, we keep in touch by the monthly Conscious Connections of the IQBC on Zoom as every year, which have their focus on „Arts and Meditation“. They will last until the coming conference.

Workshops

Jemarc Axinto (he, she, they): Queer Liberation as the Path of Awakening (Workshop)

Queer identity has been ever present since Ancient Mesopotamia. Yet, through the centuries and especially most recently, Queer oppression has risen. In response to these levels of oppression, our community has established cultural touchstones to establish Queer Identity beyond having a romantic or sexual interest in someone of the same Sex, or having a Gender identity outside of the binary. Yet, Queerness exists beyond these touch stones. In a world of impermanence, what it means to be Queer exists beyond anything we perceive to be solid. Queerness is the truest state of being when embraced as a state of NonDuality. Queerness doesn't just stand in "opposition" to Cis-Heteronormativity. In fact, Queerness fully embodied is a Nondualistic state of being. This can only be achieved by breaking down the barriers that limit what it means to live in a Queer body. If you are eager to understand how your Queer identity no longer needs to be limited by Duality, join in on this discussion and explore how you might awaken to your own Path of Liberation through your Queer Identity.

In this profound class you will explore:

- Queerness and NonDuality
- Shunyata and Creating Your Own Meaning
- Clinging to Queerness
- Empowering Metta
- Being the Gift

In this profound Master Class, Jemarc Axinto – The Spiritual Geek – will be guiding participants of the 3rd IQBC in a deep exploration of their Queer Identity and their relationship with what it means to be Queer. You will develop a loving relationship with yourself as a Queer person, and even beyond Queer identity. Come learn how Queer Liberation is a radical path to transforming the world into one of love and healing.

Jemarc Axinto (he, she, they): Finding Yourself in the Bardos – How Doctor Who Teaches Compassion in the Bardos of Death and Rebirth (Workshop)

15 min plus Q&A

In this profound Master Class, Jemarc Axinto – The Spiritual Geek – will be guiding participants of the 3rd IQBC in a deep exploration of finding oneself in the Bardos, just as the Doctor does every time they regenerate. We are all in the Bardos of Life currently, and it is only with a profound connection to our own Authenticity and with the Courage to accept our ever-changing states of being that we can achieve liberation. Come learn how to live like the radical Bodhisattva, The Doctor, and co-create a world of radically compassionate and authentic beings.

Jemarc Axinto (he, she, they): The Spiritual Playground: Workshop

In this profound Somatic Class, Jemarc Axinto – The Spiritual Geek – will be guiding participants of the 3rd IQBC in a unique modality to safely navigate and experience Shadowy emotions. You are meant to live in a world where you can feel all that there is to feel without attempting to fix or fixate. Drop back into a responseable state of being by courageously inviting everything to live within you. The Spiritual Playground is for you who is eager to know what it is to feel completely embodied and outside of the realm of overthinking. Come and Awaken your Inner Diva and play with Sangha in The Spiritual Playground.

Noire LaZard (she, her): Drawing and Intersection

Drawing has been my lifelong personal exploration of curiosity, patience-testing and willpower. No one tells you how hard it is maintaining laser-focus whilst dealing with life's challenges. Free association is how I have best described my approach to work recently. It's all the details (and even vague memories) of times of joy and pain. The new techniques and the old ones that have stayed with me for as long as I can recall. All I can offer is don't doubt the reluctant strokes because those will probably inspire another piece. Drawing is my meditation on purpose and faith. The faith that willed me to sketch one morning may be the strength needed to see another medical opinion.

And yes, I'm queer, black and disabled. This intersectionality is relatively new because I've struggled with self-acceptance of the disabled part of my existence. It's not who I am but in one too many occasions — having a disability challenged me as to why I don't acknowledge that part of me. And as my practice requires a huge degree of detail, I must bring to light to how it informs my practice. Leaning on influences from undergraduate work to cityscapes from previous residents, the process is all reflective but funneled down into this current aesthetic. It's all abstracted traces from a confluence of sketches. Ultimately, the end result is always a surprise because the spontaneity is the ride. Now, where it ends up is all a game of problem solving and willpower.

Kyle Neo (he, him): Buddhist Toolkit I and II

Rainbodhi Singapore presents
Buddhist Toolkit for LGBTQIA+
Workshop

Objectives of Buddhist Toolkit for LGBTQIA+ Workshop Series

1. Give a platform for people to discuss spirituality (Buddhist inspired) and their sexual orientation and gender identities through the Buddha's teaching of 4 immeasurable.
2. Creating a safe space to improve well-being for people who identify as LGBTQIA+ and their carers/ family members
3. Share LGBTQIA+ specific resources that everyone can apply/practice the Buddha Dharma to improve everyday life, transcending sexual, racial and cultural identities.

Extended Objectives (for website/ facebook) Rainbodhi Singapore is a collective of Buddhist or Buddhist-inspired people who realize that there are limited spaces and inclusivity from Buddhist groups to create safer, and more open platform for LGBTQIA+ and Buddhists. Members identify as heterosexual and LGBTQIA+, welcomes Non-Buddhists or Buddhists affiliated with any Buddhist tradition to explore ways that may be unintentionally overlooked or excluded in our usual Buddhist practices, how we as gay, lesbian, bisexual, pansexual, asexual, transgender, genderqueer and intersex individuals can incorporate the Buddhist teachings in our everyday lives. In addition, it aims to provide a platform for family members on how to cope with the coming out transition and allows them to understand from the Buddhism stand point on LGBTQIA+.

2-part series workshop in 2 days.

28 th October 2023 (Saturday) – 3pm – 4.30pm Singapore Time

Session 1 – 1 hour and 30 mins

Time Duration Activities Comment

3pm 10 mins Introduction to the 4 immeasurables: Equanimity, Loving Kindness, Compassion, and Sympathetic Joy

<https://www.namchak.org/community/blog/what-are-the-four-immeasurables/>

3:10pm 10 mins A detailed introduction to the first immeasurable: Loving Kindness
Before we start, we can try to do some breathing exercise

3:20pm 20 mins Starting with self-love first:

Write a Self-Compassion Letter and email it back to yourself.

Research has shown that writing self-compassionate letters to ourselves can decrease depression and increase happiness. So try to write out something kind to yourself, talking to yourself like you're a child or someone in need of kindness. Here is a self-compassion exercise that can help you build this skill.

<https://www.berkeleywellbeing.com/self-compassion-exercise.html>

3:40pm 5mins Break

3:45pm 10 mins A detailed introduction to the second immeasurable:
Loving-kindness

3:55pm 20 mins With that loving kindness you have generated for yourself, now expand it and send it to others. Transform this loving-kindness into compassion, draw out this energy and create a drawing where you can send it to others.

<https://creativityintherapy.com/2017/05/music-mindful-art/>

4:15pm 15mins Sharing, Reflection and Closing

29 th October 2023 (Sunday) – 3pm – 4.30pm Singapore Time

Session 2 – I hour and 30 mins

Time Duration Activities Comment

3pm 10 mins Introduction to the 4 immeasurable: Equanimity, Loving Kindness, Compassion, and Sympathetic Joy

<https://www.namchak.org/community/blog/what-are-the-four-immeasurables/>

3:10pm 10 mins A detailed introduction to the third immeasurable: Compassion

3:20pm 20 mins Expressing Gratitude: Creating a List of People, Things, and Events You Are Thankful For.

To cultivate gratitude, make a list of notable people, things, or events that have made valuable contributions to the world.

Reflect on each one and acknowledge the positive impact they have had on others and your life. Rejoice in their efforts!

Try adding 3 items to your list each day and build it into your daily schedule to stay consistent.

3:40pm 5mins Break

3:45pm 10mins A detailed introduction to the Fourth immeasurable: Equanimity

3:55pm 20mins Role Play Exercise

In the role play exercise, it's important to first establish the scenario that triggers the anger. This could be a disagreement with a colleague, a frustrating situation at home, or anything else that tends to cause the person to feel angry.

Once the scenario has been established, the role play can begin. One person can take on the role of the angry person, while the other person takes on the role of the manager who needs to help them manage their anger.

The manager can start by acknowledging the person's feelings and validating them. This can help the person feel heard and understood, which can go a long way in diffusing their anger.

Next, the manager can help the person identify the source of their anger and explore alternative ways of expressing their emotions. This could involve deep breathing exercises, taking a break to cool down, or finding a different way to communicate their frustrations.

The role play exercise can be repeated with different scenarios to help the person build their skills in managing their anger. With practice, they can learn to recognize their triggers and respond in a more constructive way.

<https://turningtide.org.uk/toolkit/nonviolent-communication-roleplay/>

<https://www.nvcassessment.eu/roleplays>

Watching a video and do your reflection

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6jbCdVIKzB0&ab_channel=YoursWisely

4:15pm 15mins Sharing, Reflection and Closing

Participants will require a good audio and video cam for online session

And also, some recycled paper, note pad to write in.

Good coloring mediums like crayons, color pencils or markers

Pencils or Pen for drawing.

A simple folders to keep everything you have drawn and written for future reflection.

Jampa Wurst Dharma Rap (Gender all over the World)

This Workshop will introduce the attendees to Dharma Rap, founded in 2008 by Jampa Wurst PhD aka DJ Jampa Sausage, which is their rapper name, s. <https://www.drwurst.de/dj-jampa-sausage/>

Since their first performance in 2008 on a Buddhist conference in Mongolia, Ulaan Baatar, this form of Conscious Rap has become a tradition in various conferences, and events, among Buddhist nunneries and monasteries, schools, and other institutions around the world, s. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NPew5tMFOSw>

Dharma Rap is a playful means for young and elder people, because it uses rhymes to remember things better, like the reciting of sadhanas well-known from Tibetan Buddhist nunneries and monasteries.

Dharma Rap uses this means to speak in rhymes about Buddhist ethics, being bored or burnt out in school or job, nature or climate catastrophe, politics, feminism, diversity, gender identity and much more, s. <https://www.drwurst.de/publikationen-raps/>

This time the topic is gender all over the world, because queers or 2SLGBTQIA+ people have to face difficulties, bullying, prejudices, torture, and death, because of their gender and sexuality, depending on the country or continent they live, s. <https://www.drwurst.de.....>

We will explore, what our gender identity means to us in the surrounding we live and how we can live safely and happy with the gender we identify.

Sibling Yonten (they, them): Earth Meditation and Inclusivity Workshop

Sibling Yonten offered an Earth meditation, making clear the interconnectedness between all and a talk/teaching or workshop as a possible shining/guiding light of one person's experience of accessibility & inclusiveness of the Buddhist path, from the viewpoint of a practitioner who shares a body with Neuro-divergence & disability. They will offer some insight & strategies that have helped them navigate this sometimes challenging, but essential inclusivity within, the Maha Sangha & beyond.

Anthony (Tony) Arrien (he, him): Current Trends in Gender Identity and Best Practices for LGBTQ+ Allies

After going over basic terminology about Gender, Sexual Orientation and LGBTQIA people in society, the growing prevalence of Non Binary identification is discussed. The presentation highlights the societal stresses on TGNCNB youth and adults, and how those stresses are manifesting in the changing mental health statistics. We show how this minority stress correlates with intersectionality and hate crime. Intersectionality and neurodiversity is examined and how it further relates to persecuted for being LGBTQ+. After showing the current GLSEN School Climate Survey, we will discuss techniques of how to advocate for someone who is being disrespected or bullied using ideas from the Zero Indifference Guide. After showing the disturbing trends in LGBTQ+ legislation across the US, Anthony will contrast the impact of recent New York State legislation that protects TGNCNB students from harassment, and the impact of the Gender Recognition Act.

Ceikaiyia Cheeks (she, her): Healing with Film

Summary: Nowadays, healing is more important to us now than ever. However, healing can come in many forms. For me, it happens to be Film. In my discussion, I will talk about how my new short film called "One Day Soon" helps me show others how I want to heal my soul moving forward.

Stephanie Kolton (she, her): Talking in Circles: The Importance of Peer Support for Health and Wellbeing (Seminar)

- Duration 15 minute presentation
- 30 minute Q&A
- Visual aid PowerPoint

Abstract

Marginalised communities experience significant difficulties accessing healthcare, resulting in lower self-care and self-empowerment, greater depression and anxiety, and higher probability of dis-regulated or undiagnosed health conditions and emotional distress. In particular, racial and ethnic disparities and other factors including age, sexuality, gender identity, physical ability, and socio-economic disadvantage create barriers to accessing primary health and behavioural care for as much as 50% of the population. Effective peer support can have a dramatic positive effect on health and wellness. Studies show that availability of effective peer support builds community, improves personal health outcomes, and improves quality of life, while also reducing stress on healthcare systems and reducing costs for patients and providers. Community based, facilitator led peer support has also been demonstrated in studies to improve empowerment and social ability, and to reduce internalised stigma (i.e. Internalised transphobia and homophobia) when compared to one-to-one counselling and inpatient behavioural health services. In this seminar, we will discuss the importance of peer facilitated support services in the Transgender, Non-Binary, Gender Non-Confirming, and Intersex community, and its effects on self-realisation, self-care, internalised transphobia, and emotional and social wellbeing.

In my years as a facilitator for peer-led transgender support groups, I've seen how the transgender community's lack of access to the services addressing our most basic needs, especially health and wellness services, has led to often critically negative outcomes. Young, BIPOC, and immigrant transgender people are particularly vulnerable to these impacts.

As was outlined recently by Lisa A. Cooper, MD, MPH in the New England Journal of Medicine, racial and ethnic disparities and other obstacles including age, physical ability, and socio-economic disadvantage create barriers to accessing primary behavioural care for as much as 50% of the population. These barriers lead to greater loss of healthcare privilege and greater costs for individuals and providers. The transgender, non-binary, gender non-conforming, and intersex (TNBGNCI) community experiences these barriers to care acutely.

We know that there are low-cost interventions that can help to address some of these obstacles. Specifically, studies show that peer support builds community, improves personal health outcomes, and improves quality of life. In fact, in a recent study published by Mental Health America, data suggests that effective peer support leads to a:

- 48% reduction in people needing inpatient mental health services;
- 62% decrease in the number of inpatient mental health service days required;
- 28% increase in use of outpatient mental health services; and
- 47% reduction in overall mental health costs.

This is the goal: to ensure that TNBGNCI community members have access to the support and information they need to live healthier, safer, and more fulfilling lives.

In this seminar, we will discuss the vital role which qualified and effective peer support service has on the transgender, non-binary, gender non-confirming and intersex community. We will explore

- how to create and offer a safe place for TNBGNCI people to share and grow and experience community in a nurturing and supportive environment.
- the particular sensitivities required to serve a diverse community with many intersectional needs and identities,

- fostering social equity for TNGBNCI adults, youth, and families by providing the community support needed to achieve emotional wellness and personal growth for all gender-expansive people. Following our approximately fifteen (15) minute presentation with visual aids, we will have a fifteen to twenty (15-20) minute open session of question and answers. If time allows we will also engage in a ten to fifteen (10-15) minute role play of an actual peer support group service so that participants may experience how the space is created and how facilitators can foster safe sharing and community generation.

Seminar: Deep Listening Circle

Stephanie Joy Kolton

Patchwork Transgender Peer Support

stephaniej@transpatchwork.org

30 July 2023

Seminar Deep Listening Circle

Duration 15 minute presentation

30 minute Q&A

Visual aid PowerPoint

Participants Limited to 12 persons

Description: In this workshop, participants can experience the open sharing and community which occurs within a circle of like individuals using active listening skills and one dialogue. The TNBGNCI deep listening circle is a different kind of peer group. In this space, the group participants discuss one topic or theme brought by the facilitator. The facilitator will discuss the topic in general terms, then ask each participant in turn for their thoughts or comments, feelings or impressions relating to that topic. Participants are encouraged but not required to share. Taking a moment of silence or quiet reflection is also perfectly acceptable.

Once all participants in the space have had an opportunity weigh in on the topic, the floor is open to free discussion. Participants are invited to share how others' words and emotions have affected them, questions that arose during the sharing, or concerns they feel having heard all the different thoughts and opinions. Discussion is fluid and more freeform than traditional peer groups, and directed more dynamically by the facilitator.

Unlike more common forms of peer groups in which participants share in a remote fashion, in a deep listening circle crosstalk (or directly responding or answering to the conveyed messages of other participants) is encouraged to foster a free flow of thoughts and ideas. However participants are still required use "I" statements, speaking only from one's own lived experience, and to refrain from giving advice or speaking in a place of judgement or with disregard for another's lived experience. In this session, participants are strongly admonished to refrain from any type of aggressive, abusive, or discriminatory speech or behaviour. Participants are also asked to please also be aware of micro-aggressions, as these can be very triggering. Microaggressions include statements which convey thoughts or emotions that stigmatise a marginalised group.

B Leavitt (they, them): Qi Gong Workshop

In this session, we will use gentle, flowing movements to meet, greet and enjoy our inner energetic existence. hopefully, you can leave with a simple and satisfactory practice that you can incorporate into your daily life. No prior qigong experience required. The movements can be done in any garb and standing, seated or lying down.

Panel: Gender and Buddhism

Stephen Kerry (they, them): Gender & Buddhism

In 2019, the author began a research project into the intersection of Buddhism and sexualities and sex/gender diversity among Australia's LGBTQIA+ communities. In 2021, they presented the findings of the first stage of this project (i.e. online survey) at the first IQBC. Since then, the author has been undertaking the second stage of the project (i.e. in-depth interviews) and, to date, they have conducted interviews with 25 Australian LGBTQIA+ Buddhists. Although interviews are ongoing, the author would like to take this opportunity to present some preliminary findings. One theme that appears to be emerging is that some western Buddhist traditions are struggling to accommodate trans and non-binary practitioners, especially when those traditions enforce gender-segregation. Having said that, trans and non-binary practitioners also see this as an opportunity to start a conversation with their sanghas about what it means to be trans and non-binary and Buddhist.

Elizabeth (Liz) Napp (she, her): Misfits, Outcasts, and the Revolutionary Reality of Buddhism

Buddhism spread on the Silk Roads, a network of trading routes from China through Central Asia to the Eastern Mediterranean coast. Traditionally, in many cultures, merchants had low status, particularly in Confucianism where merchants were viewed as violating the principle of filial piety. A son could not properly honor parents and ancestors when wandering about the world in search of base concerns like making money. Buddhism, however, was different. It spoke of the universal condition, of the shackles of desire, and of the nature of mind. It welcomed all. Yet in its earliest stages, Buddhism was impacted by the patriarchy of its time. It was said that the Buddha reluctantly admitted his mother-in-law and wife into monastic orders but only after advocacy by his beloved disciple, Ananda, on behalf of the women. In this sense, Buddhism was conflicted in its own sense of universality. Was it only universal regarding the human condition in relation to males? Even in the classical world, most societies were built upon binary gender systems that relegated the female to not quite human and not quite capable of the same intellectual rigors of the male. Patriarchy existed before Siddhartha's enlightenment under the Bodhi tree and continued into his Buddhahood. Yet to write Buddhism off as patriarchal is to miss the magic of those Silk Road merchants. The people who supported those earliest monasteries and popularized the practices were largely people of the lowest levels of society. Wealth was not an indicator of status in the old world. In agricultural societies, land was power and merchants were not attached to parcels of land. They were not landlords. They were wanderers over deserts and mountains. They were travelers often moving from home to home and not particularly connected to the lands from which their roaming began. While commerce is not gender, it still speaks to the complexities of Buddhism as practiced by lay people and Buddhism as practiced within the monasteries. Buddhism has always attracted the misfits and outcasts of society.

At its core, the primary appeal to most lay Buddhists is its honesty. In its Four Noble Truths, the Buddha comes right out and states what most seekers intimately know: life is not quite what the seeker imagines. Like a beautiful painting with an imperfection, life is never quite what the seeker is seeking. There is suffering. Beloved objects age and pass. Dreams materialize in ways not quite imagined. Things change. After this recognition of imperfection and impermanence, the seeker wonders how to live in a world where suffering and impermanence are part of life. The seeker learns that it is not the nature of life but the nature of mind that causes this suffering. It is the nature of things to age and to pass. The mind wants permanence. The mind wants what it wants. It is not nature but the nature of mind that must be examined. The Truths move on to show the end of suffering and the path to the end of suffering. The appeal of Buddhism is not male. That appeal of Buddhism is not female. The appeal of Buddhism is beyond gender. It is the universal reality of the human condition. While the scholars debated, the merchants used their wealth and connections to support the monasteries and spread the message. The very proliferation of the Dharma was due to the actions and activities of the lowest status members of society. In the modern world of money, it is hard to imagine that in terms of status, merchants had even lower status than peasants because peasants were connected to agricultural lands and the fruits of farming. Merchants were just misfits and outcasts.

So, how does all of this connect to Buddhism today? For many individuals, there is the recognition that gender is a social and cultural construct. What does it mean to be male? What does it mean to be female? Societal answers are almost always in regards to characteristics of the mind. A man does not cry. A woman is a caregiver. Yet humans are complex. They manifest many different emotions and responses. For some humans, the roles they are assigned are accepted and never challenged. Yet others never quite feel that the assigned roles reflect their authentic selves. They become like the merchants on the Silk Roads. They travel through deserts and over mountains. They follow their own routes to their own destinations. In their wanderings, they meet allies and encounter dangers but still they go in search of their authentic selves. They come to intimately

know the nature of mind because they have the courage to examine it. All Buddhist practice requires the courage to know the mind. In their willingness to look beyond form to the innermost sense of self, they move beyond the assigned self to the authentic self.

The authentic self is the revolutionary practice and promise of Buddhism. In Buddhism, there is no shore of certainty to cling to. In Buddhism, the waters are deep and the seeker goes into uncertainty with the knowledge that others have gone before and that in that sea of uncertainty, liberation occurs. Indeed only in the sea of uncertainty does liberation occur. All things change and pass but there is a path to the end of suffering and it is in the giving up of forms and the giving up of stories and the giving up of certainties. As in the Heart Sutra, nothing is born and nothing dies. How easily the Heart Sutra could include there is no male and there is no female. Liberation is not a form. Liberation is beyond form. Liberation is the gateless gate. Liberation is gone fully. Liberation is beyond and yet it is here too.

Oh, but it is frightening to recognize that there is no shore to cling to. There is no certainty. When I was a child, I had a toy chest. Somehow a statue of a Laughing Buddha appeared in the toy chest. I was always terrified of it. For some reason, I felt that I could not throw it away. It felt like some kind of talisman. Whenever I found it, I would stuff it to the bottom of the toy chest, hoping to not see it again. Inevitably, it would rise to the top of the toy chest only to frighten me again. As a teenager, I discovered Buddhist teachings in New Age bookshops of the eighties. When I read about Siddhartha's experiences, I was frightened again. There is sickness. There is old age. There is death. Like Siddhartha turning to his servant, Channa, I wanted to know if there was a way to avoid this suffering but as Channa said, these things come to all. I did not want to hear that but I knew that there was a promise beyond this suffering. I knew that there was a way out of suffering. I did not stuff these insights to the bottom of the toy chest. I was open to learning.

In the world today, some people are not terrified of sickness, old age, and death. They just do not look in those directions and hope they are immune to the suffering that befalls us all. Instead they look to the gender outlaws and become furious when people go in search of their authentic selves as if these individuals are causing the complete breakdown of the worlds they know. They want certainty. They become aggressive and argumentative but beneath their anger is fear. The world is always changing. There is no certainty. It is not the liberation of the individual that destroys society. It is the lack of cooperation and compassion that destroys society. The gender outlaws like the merchants on the Silk Roads are not embraced by society but pointing the way to new ways of living that are of great benefit to humanity. Today, economists know that trade is one of the pillars of uplifting people economically and alleviating the worst form of violence - as Gandhi noted - poverty. The gender outlaws also point to new ways of living that are of great benefit to humanity. The person who embraces the full complexities of all genders cultivates the finest qualities of humanity: courage and care, action and reflection, yin and yang.

Buddhism is not a practice of forms. It is not ritualistic although rituals are part of practice. Buddhism is liberation. It is intimate knowledge of the mind. It is seeing the seer. Yes, Buddhism is seeing the seer in the self. It is to see the mind in its machinations and to become aware. Buddhism is liberation and it is not found in the comfort of the known. It requires the courage of the seeker. It requires the willingness to travel through the deserts and over the mountains to worlds not imagined but worlds that will reveal themselves through practice. It is the revolutionary promise of Buddhism that beneath the forms is the authentically, liberated self. No male. No female. No beginning. No end. Beyond. Beyond. Beyond the Gateless Gate. Beyond Gender.

Kody Muncaster (they, them): Queer Approaches to Trans(forming) Buddhist Studies

Kody Muncaster, PhD Candidate

Queer people have long been ignored in Buddhist studies, even within work on engaged Buddhism. In addition, there is very little work on trans people in Buddhism, though the anthology *Transcending* along with a couple of articles and book chapters have made a strong impact and paved the way for future work. Over the past two years, I presented at talks on queer and trans people in Buddhism at IQBC; this talk is the culmination of that work. I will present on a book that I am currently writing, under contract with Sumeru Press, provisionally titled *Queer Engaged Buddhism: Trans(forming) Buddhist Studies*. I will give a brief overview of the current plan for what readers can expect from the book's chapters when it is published in 2024. This is a mix of an academic and practitioner book, offering an accessible but deep exploration of Buddhist studies and queer theory (with an emphasis on trans and intersex communities) while also including meditations for queer and trans people. I have included summaries of the chapters below:

Chapter 1: Towards a Queer Buddhist Hermeneutics: Reparative Readings of Queer and Trans Buddhist Histories

Queerness in Buddhism is an evolving debate that ranges from claims of neutrality to explicit support, to homophobia. This chapter will begin by discussing the current landscape of existing work on gay people in Buddhist hermeneutics and in liturgical linguistics. The chapter will then discuss such interpretations in relation to the cultural values and deconstructs the silences on issues such as femmophobia, the hatred of femininity, and interphobia, discrimination against intersex people. A queer Buddhist hermeneutics will be explored, examining Mahāyāna sutras and the work of Shantideva. Finally, consideration will be given to the contemporary state of queer people in Buddhism in diverse cultures.

Chapter 2: Trans Bodhisattvas, Queer Practices: Avalokitesvara, Tonglen, and HIV/AIDS

This chapter will explore shifts in the representation of Avalokitesvara's genders across cultures, including in their Kuan Yin form. Cathryn Bailey explains that the erroneous assertions that Kuan Yin was depicted as female due to the association of compassion with the feminine are complicated by the fact that compassion has historically been a masculinized quality in China (Bailey, 2009, p.178) She asserts Avalokitesvara is still sometimes depicted as male and as androgynous; thus is it not accurate to claim that Avalokitesvara "used to be" male and is now female (Bailey, 2009, p. 178). I will put Jose Munoz's (2019) work on the challenges in archiving queerness due to its ephemerality in conversation with Bailey's to argue that while it may appear anachronistic to use contemporary labels for the bodhisattva, such labels can clarify Buddhism's relationship with queerness. I will then discuss tonglen as a corporeal and affective practice that is inherently queer (read: counterintuitive) and I will explore the connections between tonglen and Avalokitesvara in Buddhist literature (Drolma, 2019) along with the usage of tonglen during the height of the AIDS pandemic (Zopa, 2001, p. 13).

Chapter 3: Non-Binary Phenomenologies, Non-Duality, and Emptiness

This chapter will consider the implications of non-dualistic Buddhist philosophy for post-structural queer theory through an examination of non-binary identity. The chapter will begin with a discussion of the non-Self doctrine and how this can be co-opted to marginalize queer people. The concept of non-Self will be considered in relation to Michel Foucault's (1990) work on the discursive formation of the homosexual as a category of being and Judith Butler's (2002) work on gender performativity, the notion that gender is reified by discourse. The chapter will discuss how non-binary identities can be seen as an extension of the Buddhist concept of non-dualism. The chapter will argue that whereas Buddhist scholars such as Shantideva (1985) apply non-dualistic philosophy to argue that there is no separation between self/Other, non-binary identity can be seen

to extend this to argue that the separations between male/female and masculine/feminine are socially constructed, or, in Buddhist terms, empty of inherent existence. I will also explore the use of yidam meditation in the Vajrayana tradition to mentally embody another gender.

Chapter 4: The Queer Temporalities of Buddhism: Queer Phenomenology, Meditation, and Transcending the Gender Binary

I will use queer phenomenology (Ahmed, 2006) to examine how Buddhist modernist approaches to mindfulness meditation emphasis on present-time awareness rids meditation of its more mystical elements. Clementine Morrigan (2017) conceptualizes ‘queer trauma time’ to argue that queer peoples’ experiences of time are often affected by trauma, leaving them haunted by the past and hypervigilant about the future (p. 54). While an excess of such cognitive-temporal shifts may be unsettling, Morrigan (2017) argues that such a concept of time should not be pathologized (p. 56). Those on the bodhisattva path are not hyper-focused on the present, the path emulates the Buddha’s past and emphasizes engaging in wholesome actions in hopes of a future favorable rebirth in which one is able to teach the Dharma. Lee Edelman’s (2004) work on queer anti-relationism argues that we should resist the heteronormative notion that we must centre our lives and activism around the notion of a better future for our imagined children (p. 29). Conversely, Jose Munoz (2019) argues that there must be room within queer theory for a queer utopianism, using a methodology of hope (p. 4). Eve Kosofsky Sedgwick discusses the paranoid approach to queer theory, meaning the excessive use of scholarly critique, and argues for a reparative approach, one that allows for positive possibilities and is steeped in an affect of hope. I will use Sedgwick’s (2003) reparative reading to argue that the sexism seen Buddhist notions that women must become male to achieve higher spiritual states (see, for example, Bca.X.30 and the Devadatta Chapter of the Lotus Sutra [Reeves, 2008, p. 253]), may simultaneously be read as affirming trans possibilities. The critique of paranoid reading in this context is not to see those who point out such sexism as literally paranoid, but rather, a reparative approach will be used to argue that these passages may be both sexist and trans-affirming at the same time; reparative reading allows for faults and positive qualities to co-exist. I will apply queer utopianism to the soteriological bodhisattva goal not to argue that bodhisattvas are in search of some imagined utopia, but to suggest that an affect of hope undergirds the bodhisattva path.

Arts

Iden.t.t (he, they): Singer

is a singer and performer on various platforms like Instagram, Spotify, Distrocid etc. and shared five short movies on gather.town on a virtual cinema created for them, like their song „Take a Breath“, Queerphoria 1 and 2, and others.

Noire LaZard (she, her): Drawing, Exhibition

Is an artist, who shares their cube arts on Instagram, but also decided to have a new exhibition with her drawings on gather.town. One can see the amazing development of her arts of cubes of black and white or in colors being interconnected, so that the one who watches her arts can float through the different dimensions.

Ceikaiyia Cheeks (she, her): Film

is a young film director, who makes short movies, especially on YouTube, but also shared two of her films on gather.town in a cinema created for her.

Jampa Wurst PhD (they, them)

is an artist with a digital atelier and shared some of her paintings (oil, acrylic) on gather.town at an exhibition.

Icaro Matias (he, him)

shared his book, his master thesis, on gather.town with the title: „The Buddhist Attitude towards Dissident Sexuality and the Contemporary Emergence of LGBTI+ Buddhist Communities as a Socially Engaged Movement“.

Contributors

Keynote Speaker: Lama Rod Owens (he, him)

Lama Rod Owens is a Black Buddhist Southern Queen. An international influencer with a Master of Divinity degree in Buddhist Studies from Harvard Divinity School. Author of *Love and Rage: The Path of Liberation through Anger* and co-author of *Radical Dharma: Talking Race, Love and Liberation*, his teachings center on freedom, self-expression, and radical self-care.

A leading voice in a new generation of Buddhist teachers with over 11 years of experience, Lama Rod activates the intersections of his identity to create a platform that's very natural, engaging, and inclusive. Applauded for his mastery in balancing weighty topics with a sense of lightness, the Queen has been featured by various national and international news outlets.

Highly sought after for talks, retreats, and workshops, his mission is showing you how to heal and free yourself. Wanna keep tabs on what Lama Rod is doing next? Be sure to sign up for his email list at <https://lamarod.us12.list-manage.com/subscribe?u=9f8f3469743a3af72f569d1f6&id=ceacabce2> Stay tuned to his website for upcoming offerings at <https://www.lamarod.com/events> for bookings and other requests at <https://www.lamarod.com/contact>.

Workshop Contributors

Jemarc Axinto (they, she, he)

Jemarc Axinto (They/She/He) is a Filipinx, Nonbinary, Trauma Recovery, Creativity & Authenticity coach with a deep practice rooted in Vajryana Buddhism and a profoundly theosophic view of spirituality and wellness. They believe that the path to healing isn't solely found in one space, but is about the deep integration of modern day science with ancient philosophy and wisdom. They have dedicated a decade of their life to the actualization of a mind, body, spirit balanced no longer withheld by trauma, labels, and roles. They've turned this deep study into an alchemical process to empower everyone they meet into actualizing their most authentic selves and radically rewiring their brains to heal trauma at its root in the nervous system. Jemarc's unique approach to healing is one that does not reject anyone so long as they keep their hearts open to the Brahmaviharas. They believe that healing isn't about restricting oneself to one path, but rather about finding your own path on the path.

Noire La Zard (she, her)

Brandi "Noire" La Zard was raised in Houston, Texas. La Zard received her BFA (Individualized Film/Video/Performance and Drawing) from California College of the Arts in San Francisco/Oakland. Her work has been selected and featured in the Creative Quarterly, as one of the national finalists in the Fine Art Professional category for the No. 27 circulation. She's also featured in WMN Zine publication dedicated to artists living with disabilities. Ms. La Zard exhibited work in the group exhibition Bombay Sapphire Artisan Series – Regional – Houston Museum of African American Culture, Houston, Texas. La Zard currently lives and works in Houston, Texas: „My work explores my life-long curiosity and fascination with form. Specifically, typography and architecture have directly influenced my artistic approach, aesthetic. The forms are created through free association; in addition, predetermined forms are used as the catalyst to develop the overall composition. My studies in graphic design, typography, architecture, abstract constructivism, and pop art have shaped my aesthetic, thus far, in the majority of works to date. Merging gestural mark-making with structured line-drawing dominates the overall composition. In this realm of competing styles of mark-making (gestural, precision mark-making), the works highlight the desire to create freedom, harmony, and balance between those worlds.“

Kyle Neo (he, him)

Kyle Neo is a freelance designer, writer and a Dharma practitioner. He holds a Diploma in Buddhist studies and Buddhist psychology. He aims to find deeper meaning in life through his adversary. His daily source of Vitamin “C” is Compassion. Last year, he had a good karmic connection to conduct a Buddhist Toolkit workshop for the LGBTQIA+ with a few Dharma friends under Rainbodhi. He is also the Editor in chief for an online Buddhist publication, Kusala. He is also now involved with a Buddhist Mentoring program which he hopes to share his insight with the Buddhist youth.

Jampa Wurst (they, them)

Dr. Jampa Wurst (PhD) studied comparative religion at Freie Universität Berlin, where they earned their PhD in 1999. In their studies, they conducted field work among Tibetan Buddhist nunneries in exile India. They was ordained twice with white robes in Theravada Buddhism. From 1991 – 1999 they studied at the Tibetan Centre in Hamburg the “7 Years Systematic Studies of Buddhism”. They finished with a certificate and earned a small yellow hat of the Gelug tradition, so similar to a teacher/acharya. Furthermore, they is a lifelong member of <https://sakyadhita.org>, has held regular workshops about LGBTQIA+ at Buddhist Conferences. As DJ Jampa Sausage, they invented <https://medium.com/@jampawurst/dharma-rap-ac5d94a231e9>, a playful medium to stir interest in education, research, Buddhist, ethics, feminism, diversity, and politics. On the artistic side, Jampa is not only a rapper but also a painter with more than 100 paintings in her <https://atelier.drwurst.de/en/>. Realizing the need for a safe space for queer Buddhists, having been bullied in their Buddhist communities, they founded the International Queer Buddhist Conferences shortly before the pandemic. Since 2021 the IQBCs have become an annual event.

Sibling Yonten (the, them)

Sib:Yonten (they/them) is a self-ordained Buddhist monastic (2017) who’s root traditions are in the Tibetan Kagyu lineage (2008). Though from 2014 has been following teachings of Ven. Thich Nhat Hanh & the Plum Village tradition. His walking of the Buddha’s path started in 1999 when he attended 3-day Lojong teachings in London, offered by the HH 14th Dalai Lama. He’s a disabled person, a military veteran & part of the LGBTQIA+ community also is the representative for PVUK’s newly forming ‘Inclusion circle for Disability and Neurodiversity’.

Anthony (Tony) Arrien (he, him)

Anthony Arrien serves on the Board of Directors of both GLSEN Lower Hudson Valley and The LOFT LGBTQ+ Community Center in White Plains in New York. Tony is a 70 year old “out” transgender man who does presentations on trans and non binary identities and intersectionality at various conferences such as Philly Trans Wellness, Hudson Valley Trans Forum, First Event in Boston, PrideWorks at Pace University and TransLives: The Intersection of Health and Law in CT. He also has done workshops at public libraries, professional organizations and K-12 schools with GLSEN for students, faculty, staff and administrators. Tony has facilitated the LOFT’s Adult Transgender Peer Support Group since 2016 and has been an activist and advocate for LGBTQ+ issues and legislation in New York State. He lives in Putnam County and is active in meetings of the Westchester PFLAG Putnam Subchapter, and has spoken at Putnam Pride events and before School Boards in defense of those who would ban LGBTQ+ books from school libraries.

Tony is a Buddhist/Unitarian whose hobbies are Plein Air oil painting plus roller and ice skating. He was a former union gaffer in the NYC Film Industry for 25 years. He is also a filmmaker who has his own production company for the purposes of doing documentaries on subjects in astronomy and the environment. He is recently retired from a job in Community Media running a local government and educational access TV station in hisTown of Putnam Valley, NY. He still serves as Chairman of

the Alliance for CommunityMedia of new York and is on the Board of the Alliance for Community Media North East Region. In his retirement he intends to keep working on legislation in New York State to create new funding streams from satellite and streaming revenues to support local media and local voices. He also hopes to do more travelling for his art and to do more LGBTQ+ cultural competency trainings to bring his lived experience to light, particularly for those who are open to learning about the minority stresses on TGNCNB individuals, for the sake of social justice.

Ceikaiyia Cheeks (she, her)

Ceikaiyia Cheeks is a 25 year old aspiring Film Director from Syracuse, NY. Recently graduated from Syracuse University with a Bachelor s Degree in Film in May 2021, this young tomboy has big plans for her city yet! Lets just hope they can handle her crazy imagination and clumsy nature! At a very young age, Ceikaiyia only knew Loneliness and Isolation, which tends to fester up every now and then. All she ever wanted was to have a connection. Lucky for her, that special want came in a form of a camera that her grandma gave her back in 7th grade. Having this camera, allowed her to create a gateway to others' lives. It gives her a chance to express her true self for the very first time! Now equipped with her universal tool for connection and communication, Ceikaiyia plans on not only just showing people, what she can do, but also show herself, what she can do! So look out everyone! A Diverse Film Director is going to emerge from Syracuse and hopes to become a big inspiration to all!

Stephanie Kolton (she, her)

Stephanie Joy Kolton (she/her) is the Founder and Executive Director of Patchwork Transgender Peer Support. A former emergency medical first responder experienced in socio-economically disadvantaged urban communities, and disaster responder specialising in pre-hospital care in uncivil and austere environments, Stephanie brings her nearly 20 years of critical crisis intervention and calm, de-escalating demeanour to serve the TNBGNCI community with her characteristic gentility and humour. In her years facilitating peer support groups, Stephanie witnessed the struggles many of her community members faced in accessing regular support and care, particularly in more underserved parts of the country. Stephanie recognised the urgent need for free access to peer support as a necessary tool for the health and wellbeing of transgender community.

In 2022, she began facilitating a small group of gender-expansive people in a deep listening circle. She saw how with every discussion, each member grew stronger and more confident in themselves, and how that confidence allowed them to lead healthier, more fulfilling lives. She knew she had to do more. So in 2023, she created Patchwork, to bring vital peer support to every transgender, non-binary, gender non- conforming, and intersex person in the country.

Patchwork

Patchwork Transgender Peer Support, a non-profit organisation, is dedicated to promoting the health and wellness of transgender, non-binary, gender non-conforming, and intersex people through engagement, support, and community. Patchwork believes freely available access to peer support and gender-related resources is one of the cornerstones of personal and emotional growth, and is key to achieving social and health equity for all gender expansive peoples.

transpatchwork.org

Instagram:

@transpatchwork

Threads:

@transpatchwork

B Leavitt (they, them)

B. Leavitt (“believe it!”) is an evolving gender fluid person who is a lawyer, parent and qigong teacher/practitioner. They have a 200 hour teaching certification from the IIQTC. Qigong has been a vital part of B’s journey and they view the practice as having profound potential for providing TGNCNB folx with a safe and powerful pathway to ease and comfort in their bodies. Focusing less on the outer appearance of qigong forms and more on the inner experience of movement, B seeks to create a fun, open and stimulating practice.

Panelists

Stephen Kerry (they, them)

Dr Stephen Kerry is a lecturer in sociology at Charles Darwin University (Darwin, Australia). Dr Kerry identifies as genderqueer non-binary, uses they/them pronouns, and has been part of Australia's LGBTQIA+ communities for 33 years. Dr Kerry has published books on the lived experiences of intersex Australians and the health needs of trans and non-binary people living in Australia's Northern Territory. Dr Kerry is a Zen Buddhist and is a member of the Melbourne Zen Group (Diamond Sangha tradition). They underwent their Jukai ceremony in 2019 and was presented with the Dharma name of 涼猿 (Liáng Yuán, cool monkey). Dr Kerry volunteers heavily in Australia's LGBTQIA+ communities and is also a volunteer telephone counsellor, they live in Melbourne with their two cats.

Elizabeth (Liz) Nett (she/her)

„Autobiographical statements are awkward for me. There are the checklist items: mother, teacher, devotee of Bodhisattva Tara, and practitioner of TM. But the core of my practice is a need for the peace that only spirituality brings. It is like a merchant travelling the Silk Roads. There is the promise of success if the journey is finished and a bit of pleasure awaits at the end of the road but in the meantime, there are deserts to survive and crevasses in mountains not to fall in. And then even at the end of the journey, there are more journeys until the final journey. Like that merchant, I need something to hold onto. I need Bodhisattva. I need meditation. I need a spiritual life. The fearless and the foolish may not but I know the perils of the journey. I need Bodhisattva.”

Kody Muncaster (them them, and iel avec accords masculins (Français))

PhD Candidate – Gender, Sexuality, & Women's Studies, Western University
Instructor – Buddhism, Psychology, & Mental Health Program, University of Toronto
Research Manager – School of Nursing, York University
HIV & HCV Outreach Coordinator – Specialty Rx's PrEPrx Clinics
Buddhist Grief Counsellor – Toronto Centre for Applied Buddhism.

Art Contributors

Iden.t.t (they, them)

They dreamed of performing ever since they were a child. They have been writing various forms of songs and poems but never had the chance to share with the world.

Much like many other LGBTQIA+ folks, Iden.t.T struggled to find their place in aa world as a child, and is so grateful to the many queercestors who paved the way to make way for them to explore their identity in music gender and tranquility, s. <https://www.identt.biz/>

Noire La Zard (she, her)

Brandi “Noire” La Zard’s biography see pages 13 and 41.

Ceikaiyia Cheeks (she, her)

Ceikaiyia Cheeks’ biography see pages 25, 39, and 43.

Jampa Wurst PhD (they, them)

Jampa Wurst’s biography, see pages 19, 42, and 40.

Icaro Matias MA (he, him)

Icaro Matias’ biography, see page 40. More info Rainbow Sangha Brazil, see <https://Budismolgbt.com.br> where Icaro Matias is a member.

Outlook

Meanwhile, since I founded the International Queer Buddhist Conferences, IQBCs, as a safe space for queer or 2SLGBTQIA+ people, who are Buddhist or mindful and respectful, this has become an annual event. The IQBCs are open not only for Buddhists or 2SLGBTQIA+ people, but also for every religion or philosophy, also if people are atheists, and allies of the queer community.

The monthly Conscious Connections of the IQBC also have become a regular event with the focus on arts and meditation.

The need for safe spaces like the annual IQBCs and their Conscious Connections are still and not only still needed. They are important because it seems that all around the world queer people have become bullies and even threatened again like in previous times.

So, this means that after the conference is before the conference!

We stay in touch monthly, but also on social media or email to support each other and to exchange ideas about the 4th IQBC, which will be held in October 2024.

Also, the 4th IQBC will provide the global queer Buddhist and mindful family with scholarly talks, workshops, and especially artsy expressions because artsy expressions make it possible for queer and Buddhist people to survive and to live in spite of difficulties by expressing themselves, their gender, their diversity, their facets among this global rainbow community. The International Queer Buddhist Conferences will be a safe space for this as long as there is this need.

On <https://iqbc.org> you will always be updated.

As I mentioned on the previous Conference Proceedings:

„May it become a tradition of further International Queer Buddhist Conferences – IQBCs - as a safe and protected place, no matter, which sexuality, gender, color or culture you belong!

May all beings be happy.

May all beings be safe, and well.

May all beings be peaceful and at ease.“

Acknowledgements

I am very grateful for my global team, who encouraged me to organize the 3rd International Queer Buddhist Conference, IQBC.

Thanks to the two allies, supporting me behind the scenes, Melanie Poech and Lukas Galke. Melanie has always been supportive, creating and being in charge of <https://iqbc.org> and taking care that everything worked on this website, uploaded photos, videos, linking with YouTube, giving me kindly advice how to spread the news via facebook, twitter, and instagram, and finally cutting and uploading the videos of the talks, after the conference had finished. She always has been in touch with me, that everything worked perfectly. Thanks to Lukas Galke, who always was there, when questions arise and encouraging Miriam to create on gather.town a site for the IQBCs. Also, I would like to thank Lukas for putting the Conference Proceedings on zenodo.org.

Miriam, whom I have been friends with since university times, studying, is, too, an ally. She offered her support, showing her facets creating this beautiful space on gather.town for us with rivers, lake, fountains, a hidden island, and exhibitions, cinemas, Library and more. Thank you! I am grateful for the support of Br. Yonten and their current support answering emails concerning questions about the helplines we provide on <https://iqbc.org>.

Thank you to Daigan, who encouraged me to again reach out to Lama Rod Owens asking for being the keynote speaker for the 3rd IQBC, and it came true this time!

I am grateful for the volunteers of my organizing team, sharing workshops and arts and also support e.g. in writing or editing English articles like Elizabeth (Liz) Napp. Encouraged by the volunteers I am sure we again will organize another beautiful International Queer Buddhist Conference, IQBC in Fall 2024!

Supplement

DJ Jampa Sausage and the Dharma Rappers

i'm a shapeshifter

i'm a shapeshifter
gender drifter
what a gifter
to the picture
of each our liberation
such freedom to be
who i want us all to be—
radically and fully you and me

Life

Starting off my life in rural UK
with no one around to say “I was OK”
it took many years along lives meandering path
to find myself experiencing true joy and learning how to laugh

not coming out until the age of 30
letting go of the hang ups of how I'd be perceived,
Though I saw myself as bi I still had questions in me.
Not understanding how to present myself and truly be.

Life had its own choice and offered an accident one day.
which eventually gifted the opportunity to ordain,
though it took me till a workshop held by James on the first I QBC
to find my umbrella and live in the radiance of gender diversity.

free

looking what we have in common
looking for stimulation and surprises
looking in your face seeing
me

let`s response
let`s dance together

giving trust and an open hand
being free in diversity

Gender1

It's about gender!
So never surrender!
Never give up,
go your path,
go your way,
walk your journey,
your trip to your goal:
„That's the way!“
The Mandalorian say(s).
To your goal, to your lib, that you can live your life free:
Walk towards your liberation.
Then you are free..
Then you can be!
„Everybody be :)

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